
COMMENTARY

COVID-19 Vaccination in Slums: Challenges and Recommendations

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Abstract:

When estimating vaccination coverage, residents of slums and rural settlements are frequently overlooked because generalized statistics rarely identify regions of a nation where vaccination promotion is lacking. Furthermore, the WHO recently recognized vaccine hesitancy as a major threat to the effective vaccination of the world population, with a sizable population either resorting to hesitancy or experiencing low vaccination coverage. This mishap is the result of numerous circumstances, including a lack of resources and technology, a lack of faith in medical facilities, logistical issues, widespread misinformation, and more. These factors play a significant role in the hesitation and inadequate immunization rates among these communities, which, in the grand scheme of things, can encourage the emergence of new variations and damage the health of the general populace. The suggested remedies would include the construction of adequate facilities, access to funding, widespread public awareness campaigns, and refuting false information about vaccination and immunization in general are all suggested as answers.

Keywords: SARS-CoV-2, COVID-19, Coronavirus, Outbreak, Rural, slums, Vaccination

BACKGROUND

In 2019, the WHO identified vaccination hesitancy as a significant threat to world health. The COVID-19 VACCINATION program, which began in 2021 in numerous nations, including Bangladesh and other African nations—Nigeria—also demonstrated the same resistance. This is brought on by a number of things, including illiteracy, inaccurate information, a lack of faith in healthcare systems, etc. particular to the context and varying over time, place, and social classes.

Slum dwellers should be the first to receive COVID-19 immunizations since they are more prone to contract the virus due to their poor living conditions and inability to follow preventive measures. We therefore aimed to understand how slum residents' attitudes and perspectives on the COVID-19 VACCINATION were changing.

INTRODUCTION

The Corona virus diseases 2019 (COVID-19) is a communicable respiratory disease caused by a new strain of coronavirus that causes illness in humans. The first known case was discovered in Wuhan, China in December 2019. It took three months for the virus to spread globally, so much so that it became a pandemic. The World Health Organization (WHO) declared the COVID-19 outbreak a pandemic in March, 2020.

While there's been a couple of developments regarding curating a remedy for the virus, vaccine development has historically proved to be the significant way of curbing the spread of viruses as well mitigating its effect upon infection. Hence safe and effective vaccines are a critical tool to control the COVID-19 pandemic.

Now speaking of vaccination coverage, approximately 30% of the world's population lives in slum settlements. These residents thus suffer from higher rates of COVID-19 infection, hospitalization, and mortality than the urban population. Moreover, COVID-19 has had a huge economic impact caused by alarming unemployment rates, which limits strict adherence to preventive measures (e.g social distancing and lockdown). Vaccination are the main strategy to decrease this COVID-19 burden. However, the lack of information regarding COVID-19 vaccine acceptance, and its challenges in slum communities may limit the success of vaccination campaigns and impact on COVID-19 vaccination coverage.

Although effective and equitable distribution of COVID-19 vaccines is a key policy priority, ensuring acceptance is just as important. Trust in vaccines as well as the institutions that administer them are key determinants of the success of any vaccination campaign.

Numerous studies have investigated willingness to take a potential COVID-19 vaccine in high-income countries and urban populations and some studies have included middle-income countries as well. Little is known however, about vaccine acceptance in rural settlements where large-scale vaccination has yet to begin. Understanding the drivers of COVID-19 vaccine acceptance is of global concern, because a lag in vaccination in any country may result in the emergence and spread of new variants that can overcome immunity conferred by vaccines and prior disease.

The aims of this study are to provide extensive information on the vaccination programme for COVID-19, challenges, together with recommendations for mitigating these challenges, with focus on Slum residents because there is evidence of effectiveness of the COVID-19 vaccines that are widely used for the immunization exercise in Africa (Pfizer/BioNTech, Moderna and Oxford/AstraZeneca) from other parts and regions of the world such as in Israel, Scotland, US, and United Kingdom.

Current efforts

Africa's largest-ever immunization drive is well underway, with COVID-19 vaccines being administered in almost all African countries. 47 African countries have joined the COVAX facility, which aims to ensure equitable access to safe and effective COVID-19 vaccines globally.

68% of the world population has received at least one dose of a COVID-19 vaccine.

12.74 billion doses have been administered globally, and 3.73 million are now administered each day. Only 22.7% of people in low-income countries have received at least one dose.(WHO)

Total COVID-19 vaccine doses administered per 100 people, Sep 29, 2022

All doses, including boosters, are counted individually.

Source: Official data collated by Our World in Data – Last updated 30 September 2022

OurWorldInData.org/coronavirus • CC BY

CHALLENGES

Despite the remarkable progress made as regards ensuring wide vaccination coverage across the continents, the momentum is however subsiding drastically in slums and rural settlements owing to numerous factors some of which are highlighted down below.

Vaccine hesitancy is a great concern which has escalated in recent years and this is owing to doubts and concerns regarding vaccine effectiveness and potential side effects, another factor is the widespread misinformation over social media regarding this subject matter which goes on brewing fear within civilians thus worsening vaccine acceptance within the majority. In some research papers COVID-19 vaccine hesitancy was also associated with younger age and low perceived importance of vaccination to protect one's family and friends while attitudes associated with its acceptance included the perception of being at high risk for COVID-19, thinking that it is a

serious disease, and the belief that the vaccine would not only protect those who would receive it but also their families, friends and community

Another reason to be wary of vaccines is how quickly they were developed. The research and approval of vaccinations often takes years, but COVID-19 vaccines are an exception. This raises concerns about the vaccinations' safety. Many individuals (especially those living in slums) think the procedure was hurried because there was such a great need for a treatment and so many rules were disregarded. However, the quick creation of the vaccine may be due to earlier studies and cutting-edge technology on the corona virus. Many people overlook this and are unwilling to be vaccinated as a result.

Availability of vaccination centers is also a challenge in COVID-19 vaccination. Many people complain about the proximity to vaccination centers and would rather stay at home than go the extra mile. The process of vaccination is not a short one and it usually begins with an online registration. Most people living in the slums do not have access to the technological devices required to register, not to talk of the knowledge required to operate such devices. The long queues to get a shot is also a cause of complaints for some people. Due to the high population in slum areas, overcrowding in vaccination centers is frequent. Many would avoid vaccination for these reasons.

Another major hurdle to vaccination programmes in slum settlements is inadequate storage facilities due to limited funds to provide cold chain systems, and maintain an organized network to monitor the vaccine distributions. This typically leads to product expiration and inactivation, which is noticeable in the majority of underdeveloped countries. These issues are more pronounced in rural areas and villages because of unstable electricity and frequent power outages, inadequate cold chain equipment and facilities, a poor road system that makes it difficult to transport vaccines and immunizers to target communities, untrained immunizers, and a lack of basic social amenities like housing and access to clean running water, which discourages the posting of health workers to villages.

The fact that some people do not view the virus as a cause for fear is another significant barrier to immunization. In contrast to Western nations, the outbreak was significantly less severe in African nations. The COVID-19 vaccination was frequently ignored by many Africans because they could not perceive a need for it. Contrary to affluent nations like the USA, the majority of African nations were not as eager to adopt vaccines.

RECOMMENDED SOLUTIONS

Raising awareness of the virus and its severity through campaigns (both online and offline) and health discussions in order to improve COVID-19 immunization in the slum. The general people must be fully informed about the virus. Debunking myths and erroneous beliefs is also important

Dispelling myths and misconceptions that discourage vaccine uptake will enable efficient rollout and achieve massive uptake by slum residents. While it is essential to have mechanisms in place that ensure a quick and unhindered allocation of COVID-19 vaccines the moment they become available, the importance of a comprehensive community sensitization is paramount and should not be undervalued.

Utilizing local heroes, well-known individuals, and celebrities to spread vaccination promotion messages may increase public acceptance of vaccines by providing more human and material resources needed to address COVID-19 vaccine hesitancy in African countries.

Additionally, the incorporation of the COVID-19 vaccine into the regular vaccination framework and as a requirement might help to fortify the public care system, promoting and increasing the acceptability of the vaccine.

It is crucial to emphasize the role of non-governmental organizations in forging strong bonds with slum dwellers. Therefore, NGOs should be encouraged and rewarded to engage with slums to spread knowledge and even help medical professionals administer vaccinations.

To further persuade slum dwellers to accept vaccination, physical rallies and campaigns should be organized to educate the public on the significance of COVID 19 vaccinations. Practical examples of the COVID 19 vaccinations should be made available at these rallies.

The government and other powerful and wealthy individuals should provide the required infrastructure since this will aid in the preservation of the vaccines and ensure the comfort of slum dwellers while receiving the vaccination.

To help slum settlements acquire and maintain storage equipment for the vaccine, grants and financial aid should be made accessible. These regions can also receive technological assistance to aid in the creation of a functional system that monitors vaccine uptake.

To assist the public in making plans for their activities, information about vaccination centers such as their location and opening and closing times should be made available. To decrease the wait times at vaccination sites, more trained staff should be hired. It should be possible to register on-site for individuals without technological expertise.

CONCLUSION

One of the most vulnerable populations for COVID-19 is the rural residents, who live in congested conditions with little access to public (health) services and other crucial elements. In these slum regions, COVID-19 vaccination still confronts several difficulties. These difficulties can however be overcome through collective efforts.

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